

1 **NLRP7 engagement in transformation and etiology of chronic disease.**

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7 We describe here NLRP7 activation (and in some cases silencing) as a signature event in circumstances
8 of sudden change in speed of cell cycle (rapid cycling induced by tumor suppressor deletion), as a direct
9 transcriptional consequence of expression of chronic disease susceptibility genes like NOD2, and in the
10 steady state in nature, in chronic human diseases including multiple sclerosis and IBD (CD). NLRP7
11 activation or silencing in resistance models suggests that this NLR possesses an advanced alarm or
12 change signal triggered by large changes in cellular or microenvironment (i.e., cancer metastasis). We
13 describe what appears to be a signature event in the etiology of human disease likely in relation to cell
14 cycle alteration recently described as a signature feature found in cells following expression of a chronic
15 disease-associated susceptibility gene, with etiologic significance following activity in the nucleus like
16 oncogene expression early in disease development or transformation. Co-regulation with TIGIT and BATF
17 suggests involvement of exhaustion signaling or NLRP7 activity during periods of senescence or
18 interactions with exhausted cells.
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